

Characterisation and synthesis of AgNPs from *Chlorophytum comosum* leaves

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Abstract- Nanoparticles exhibit advantageous attributes in diverse domains, including medicine, catalysis, and environmental remediation, owing to their elevated surface area-to-volume ratio, heightened reactivity, and distinctive physical and chemical properties. *Chlorophytum comosum* has strong antimicrobial properties against bacteria like *Bacillus subtilis* and *E.coli*, as well as fungi like *Fusarium oxysporum*, due to its high levels of tannins and phenols, despite lacking alkaloids; its extract shows significant sensitivity against *C. albicans*. Characterization of silver nanoparticles synthesized from *Chlorophytum comosum* leaves involved SEM & FTIR analysis, revealing circular and smooth morphology indicative of controlled synthesis. In conclusion, *Chlorophytum comosum* -derived nanoparticles present a compelling avenue for antimicrobial applications, demonstrating efficacy against a range of pathogens, as evidenced by their well-defined morphology and unique chemical composition.

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I INTRODUCTION-

The synthesis of nanoparticles has garnered significant attention in recent years due to their unique physical, chemical, and biological properties, which hold promise for a wide range of applications, including medicine, electronics, and environmental remediation. Among these, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are particularly notable for their potent antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and catalytic properties. Traditional methods of synthesizing AgNPs often

involve hazardous chemicals and energy-intensive processes, leading to an increased interest in green synthesis approaches that utilize biological resources.

Chlorophytum comosum, commonly known as the spider plant, is a perennial herb widely recognized for its ornamental value and air-purifying capabilities. Beyond its aesthetic appeal, *Chlorophytum comosum* possesses a rich phytochemical profile, including flavonoids, phenolics, and terpenoids, which can serve as reducing and stabilizing agents in the synthesis of AgNPs. Utilizing plant extracts for nanoparticle synthesis not only provides an eco-friendly alternative to conventional methods but also enhances the biocompatibility and potential therapeutic applications of the nanoparticles.

In this study, we explore the characterization and synthesis of AgNPs using leaf extracts from *Chlorophytum comosum*. Our approach emphasizes the green synthesis route, leveraging the natural reducing agents present in the plant extract to produce AgNPs with desirable properties. The objectives of this research are to synthesize AgNPs via a simple, environmentally benign process, characterize the physicochemical properties of the synthesized nanoparticles, and evaluate their potential applications.

We begin by preparing the leaf extract of *Chlorophytum comosum* and subsequently use it to reduce silver ions to silver nanoparticles. The synthesized AgNPs are then characterized using various analytical techniques, including UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). These techniques provide comprehensive insights into the size, shape, crystalline structure, and functional groups associated with the AgNPs.

Furthermore, we assess the antimicrobial efficacy of the synthesized AgNPs against a range of pathogenic microorganisms, demonstrating their potential for use in medical and environmental applications. By integrating the principles of green chemistry with advanced nanotechnology, this study aims to contribute to the development of sustainable and effective methods for nanoparticle synthesis.

II LITERATURE REVIEW

India's medical landscape blends ancient wisdom from Ayurveda with modern advancements in healthcare. Ayurveda, dating back over 5,000 years, emphasizes holistic well-being and is documented in texts like the Charaka Samhita and Sushruta Samhita (Patwardhan & Mashelkar, 2009). India's pharmaceutical industry is globally renowned for generic drug production, constituting about 20% of global exports (Ministry of Commerce & Industry, Government of India, 2020). In ancient times, civilizations like the Egyptians, Greeks, and Chinese unknowingly used nanoparticle-based remedies, such as gold and silver nanoparticles (Fahmy *et.al.*, 2020; Thakkar *et.al.*, 2010). Contemporary nanomedicine, exemplified by drugs like Abraxane and Doxil for cancer treatment, showcases the transformative potential of nanotechnology in healthcare (Gradishar *et.al.*, 2005; Rahman *et.al.*, 2013; Toth *et.al.*, 2009).

The spider plant is a popular indoor plant known for its beauty and ability to clean the air. It comes from South Africa and has long, curving leaves with white stripes. Studies by NASA have shown that the spider plant can remove harmful indoor pollutants like formaldehyde, xylene, and carbon monoxide, making the air in your home healthier (Wolverton *et.al.*, 1989). Plus, spider plants are safe for pets, making them a great choice for households with animals (American Society for the Prevention of Cruelty to Animals).

Traditional medicinal uses of spider plants (*Chlorophytum comosum*) have been documented in some cultures, although scientific evidence supporting these claims is limited. In traditional systems of medicine, spider plant extracts have been applied topically to wounds for their purported wound-healing properties (Kim *et.al.*, 2006). Additionally, they have been used orally to address digestive issues like stomachaches and indigestion, as well as respiratory ailments such as coughs and asthma (Patel *et.al.*, 2012). However, it's crucial to approach these traditional uses with caution and seek guidance from healthcare professionals, as rigorous scientific studies are needed to validate their efficacy and safety for medicinal purposes.

Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have gained considerable attention recently due to their unique physical and chemical characteristics and diverse applications across multiple fields such as medicine, electronics, catalysis, and environmental clean-up. These nanoparticles are typically produced using physical, chemical, or biological methods, each offering distinct advantages in terms of particle size, shape, stability, and scalability (Suresh *et.al.*, 2012). In the medical realm, AgNPs have shown promising antimicrobial properties against a wide

range of pathogens, including bacteria, viruses, and fungi, making them potential candidates for novel antimicrobial agents and wound dressings (Morones *et.al.*, 2005). Moreover, AgNPs exhibit potential in cancer therapy by selectively targeting tumor cells while minimizing harm to healthy tissues, primarily through mechanisms such as oxidative stress induction, DNA damage, and apoptosis (Xiu *et.al.*, 2012). Additionally, AgNPs have been investigated for their anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and wound-healing properties, suggesting their potential use in treating various inflammatory and degenerative diseases (Zhang *et.al.*, 2016). However, concerns about potential cytotoxicity, environmental impact, and the development of antimicrobial resistance associated with AgNPs necessitate further research to clarify their safety profile and optimize their therapeutic applications (Jena & Mohanty, 2012).

Figure:1 *Chlorophytum comosum* (spider plant)

III METHODOLOGY

Material and Methods-

The current study, "**Characterisation and synthesis of AgNPs from *Chlorophytum comosum***," was carried out at the Department of Botany at Career Point University in Kota (Rajasthan). The materials utilised, methodology used, experiments, microbial culture used and techniques are detailed below.

Chemicals and solvents

The information of all materials and chemicals used in the present study are tabulated in Table below-

Chemicals	Used for
Silver nitrate (AgNO_3)	Silver nanoparticles formation
PBS (phosphate buffer solution)	For preparing of suspension of fungal spores
Mueller Hinton agar no. 2	Determination of Antibacterial property
Sabouraud's dextrose agar, (SDA)(sub culturing)	Determination of Antifungal property
Dimethyl Sulphoxide (DMSO)	Dilution of plant extract
Ciprofloxacin	Antibacterial drug
Ketoconazole	Antifungal drug
Whatman's filter paper	AgNO_3 solution filtration

Table No.- 1 : list of the chemicals used during the experiment

Preparation of plant extract

Plant leaves were washed thoroughly with tap water 2-3 times then the leaves were again washed with distilled water. The washed leaves were then air dried. The powdered leaves were thoroughly blended with 100 millilitres of distilled water. After that solution was filtered by using (Whatman Number one) filtered paper.

Antibacterial assessment:-

The antibacterial assessment of the sample against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was conducted using the agar well diffusion method as described by Perez *et.al.*, (1990). Mueller Hinton agar no. 2 was utilized as the bacteriological medium, and the extracts were prepared at 10 mg/mL concentrations in Dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO).

Standardized inoculum of bacterial strains was added to the agar plates, and wells were created for sample administration. The experiment was repeated thrice, and inhibition zones were measured to determine antimicrobial activity. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) was established by identifying the lowest inhibitory concentration of the sample against bacterial strains.

Antifungal assessment:-

For antifungal assessment, the agar well diffusion method was employed as per Bonjar *et.al.*, (2005). Fungal strains were cultured on Sabouraud's dextrose agar, and suspensions of fungal spores were prepared and applied to the agar medium. Wells were punctured, and various dilutions of the sample were administered. The experiment was repeated thrice, and the diameter of inhibition zones was measured to assess bioactivity. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined to identify the lowest sample concentration inhibiting fungal growth.

Nanoparticle formation:-

Plant part mediated AgNPs was synthesized by using Loo *et.al.*, 2012 method. 12 milliliters of filtrate was stirred properly with 100 milliliters of 1mM AgNO₃, and was cautiously heated for 60 seconds. Then continuously stirred with the help of magnetic stirrer. Colour changes of the solution were observed.

Preliminary phytochemical screening of secondary metabolites:-

1) Tannin:

FeCl₃ test: 2 mL of plant extract was placed in a test tube. A few drops of 0.1% FeCl₃ solution were added. The presence of a blue-green, blackish-green color, or precipitate indicated the presence of tannins (Trease and Evans, 1989).

2) Alkaloids:

Mayer's reagent: Mayer's reagent is prepared by dissolving mercuric chloride (1.36 g) and potassium iodide (5 g) in water (100 mL) freshly.

For the **Mayer test**, 2 mL of plant extract is placed in a test tube. Then, 5 mL of 1% aqueous HCl is added followed by 100 µL or 4-5 drops of freshly prepared Mayer's reagent. The appearance of a buff-colored precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids (Sofowora, 1993).

3) Phenol:

A few drops of 10% ferric chloride solution were added to 2 mL of the extract. The development of a bluish-green or black color indicated the presence of phenols (Shalini & Sampathkumar, 2012).

Characterisation of nanoparticles:-

Characterization of nanoparticles is essential to understand their properties, behaviour, and potential applications.

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) analysis:

The sample was in the powdered form and the voltage used was 5.0Kv and was carefully placed on the SEM stub along with the copper grid. A working distance of 8.1 mm means that the final lens of the SEM is positioned 8.1 millimeters away from the surface of the sample. This distance can vary depending on the specific parameters set for the SEM imaging, such as the magnification level and the desired depth of focus. The image was magnified 80,000 times compared to the actual size of the sample.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis:

This method helps to identify differences in the way molecules bind together, which can provide information about the interactions between them. The x- axis representing the infrared spectrum whereas y- axis representing the amount of infrared light absorbed or transmitted by the sample.

IV Result and Discussion:

S. No	Bacterial Strains	Code	Inhibition Zone(std.)	20µl	40µl	60µl	80µl
1	<i>B.subtilis</i>	(MTCC 10619)	41 (AgNP's)	7.7 ±1.729	8.7 ±2.848	10 ±1.132	10.7 ±0.653
2	<i>B.subtilis</i>	(MTCC 10619)	35(Methanol)	7.7 ±0.653	11.3 ±1.729	12 ±1.132	14 ±1.132

Table2:-effect of *Chlorophytum comosum* leaf extract with AgNO₃ & methanol against *B. subtilis*

S.No	Bacterial Strains	Code	Inhibition Zone(std.)	20µl	40µl	60µl	80µl
1	<i>E.coli</i>	(MTCC443)	36 (AgNP's)	6.6 ±0.784	7.6 ±1.176	10.7 ±0.653	11.6 ±0.599
2	<i>E.coli</i>	(MTCC443)	37(Methanol)	0	0	10.2 ±2.267	13 ±1.96

Table3:-effect of *Chlorophytum comosum* leaf extract with AgNO₃ & methanol against *E.coli*

S.No	Fungal Strains	Code	Inhibition Zone(std.)	20µl	40µl	60µl	80µl
1	<i>C. albicans</i>	(MTCC183)	34 (AgNP's)	0	0	9.3 ±1.729	12.3 ±1.729
2	<i>C. albicans</i>	(MTCC183)	21(Methanol)	10.7 ±1.307	17.3 ±2.356	18.7 ±0.653	19.7 ±1.307

Table4:-effect of *Chlorophytum comosum* leaf extract with AgNO₃ & methanol against *C. albicans*

S.No	Fungal Strains	Code	Inhibition Zone(std.)	20µl	40µl	60µl	80µl
1	<i>F. oxysporum</i>	(MTCC1755)	22 (AgNP's)	0	8.3 ±1.729	10 ±0	11.7 ±1.729

2	<i>F. oxysporum</i>	(MTCC 1755)	22(Methanol)	0	6.7 ±0.653	7.7 ±1.307	10 ±1.132
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Table5:-effect of *Chlorophytum comosum* leaf extract with AgNO₃ & methanol against *F. oxysporum*

Phytochemical compounds	<i>Chlorophytum comosum</i> (Spider)
Tannin	++
Alkaloids	++
Phenol	+++

Table6: Preliminary phytochemical screening of secondary metabolites

Methanolic leaf extract test against microbes:

After incubation of 24 h bioactivities were determined by measuring the diameter of inhibition zone (in mm). Ketoconazole is used as antifungal drug (a positive control) and ciprofloxacin as antibacterial drug (a positive control). To identify MIC, minimum

concentration of sample in μl were used that show inhibitory activity against pathogenic fungal strains. It was observed that *C. albicans* as a fungal strain is most sensitive to the methanolic leaves extract, 19.7 ± 1.307 mm of inhibition zone in 80 μl sample test sample. On the other hand *F. oxysporum* is least sensitive to the extract, 10 ± 1.132 mm of inhibition zone in 80 μl . In case of bacterial strain not much diametric (in mm) difference is seen.

Silver nanoparticle along with the leaf extract test against microbes:

After the formation of the solution, it was poured in the 6mm depth well and was incubated overnight in the case of bacterial strains and for 5-6 days in case of fungal strains at 37°C . The presence of secondary metabolites such as tannins, phenols, is implicated in the observed antibacterial and antifungal activity, consistent with their known bioactive properties.

Preliminary phytochemical screening of secondary metabolites:

According to Trease and Evans (1989), the formation of a blue-green or blackish-green color precipitate indicates the presence of tannins in the leaves. Sofowora (1993) noted that a buff-colored precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids. Shalini and Sampathkumar (2012) demonstrated that the appearance of a bluish-green or black color indicates the presence of phenols. The tested leaf extract contains these secondary metabolites.

Figure:3 methanolic leaves extract test against *E. coli*

Figure:4 methanolic leaves extract test against *B. subtilis*

Figure:5 methanolic leaves extract test against *F. oxysporum*

Figure:6 methanolic leaves extract test against *C. albicans*

Figure:7 AgNP's test against *E. coli*

Figure:8 AgNP's test against *B. subtilis*

Figure:9 AgNP's test against *F. oxysporum*

Figure:10 AgNP's test against *C.albicans*

Figure:11 A- Tannin test control
:11 B- *Chlorophytum comosum*

Figure:12A- Alkaloid test control
:12 B- *Chlorophytum comosum*

Figure:13 A- Phenol test control
:13B- *Chlorophytum comosum*

Figure:14 *Chlorophytum comosum* AgNP's SEM characterisation showing circular and smooth nanoparticles

Figure:15 *Chlorophytum comosum* AgNP's FTIR analysis

V CONCLUSION

We can conclude that, the data showed that both the concentration of antibacterial agents and the specific bacterial strain being targeted have a significant impact on the size of inhibition zones. This suggests that adjusting the concentration of antibacterial agents as well as antifungal agents can enhance their effectiveness against certain bacterial and fungal strains. It was reported earlier as well that the antimicrobial property of the leaves extract is due to the presence of phytochemicals.

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